

Impact of Anxiety and Achievement Motivation on Colleges of Education Students' Academic Performance in Cross River State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: The study was designed to determine the impact of anxiety and achievement motivation on Colleges of Education Students' academic performance, in Cross River State of Nigeria. Three (3) research question/hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and relevant literature was reviewed covering trait and state anxieties, achievement motivation and students' academic performance generally. A survey research design was adopted which made use of a sample of Nine hundred college students each from two (2) Colleges of Education in the state. Two (2) research instruments namely; structured questionnaire, and subject scores based on their externally moderated second semester result for 2022/2023 academic session, were employed for data collection. Data analysis technique adopted was one way analysis of variance (ANOVA). All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. The result revealed significant impact of anxiety and achievement motivation on College of Education students' academic performance in Cross River State, Nigeria. Based on the research findings, it was recommended among others that qualified and conscientious guidance counsellors be sent to all Colleges of Education.

KEY WORDS: Anxiety, Achievement Motivation and Students' Academic performance

INTRODUCTION/BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Some of the problems confronting teaching and learning seem to include students' levels of anxiety and achievement motivation. Whenever there is a group of students, be it nursery, primary, secondary or tertiary, one is likely to expect different behaviours from each member of the group. There are those who are likely to be almost always withdrawn, moody, have feelings of being frustrated or are afraid that they may be frustrated in the course of completing their educational programmes and feel disappointed by almost every event in their school. These feelings make them become doubtful, solicitous, apprehensive and eager about everything in their school. They are said to be anxious.

On the other hand, there are other members of the class who would behave differently, very active, raise issues for discussion, ask questions or are always ready to attempt answering any question(s) from the lecturer. This other group of students also make friends very easily and seem to be encouraged by everything around them in the school. They are said to be motivated by the school environment and probably by conditions at home.

In all cases, the level of either anxiety or achievement motivation may positively or negatively influence students' level of performance.

In the classroom, lecturers who are frequently fond of using abusive words on students are over strict in grading, also lack concern about students' welfare, give so much information or many materials to be learnt and give insufficient or incorrect information normally help to get students frightened. This could cause anxiety among students in the class and thus affect the learning process since they have become disorganized.

On the other hand, lecturers who are interested in students' welfare, cheerful, give quality advice always to students, fair in grading students and do not use abusive words on students tend to motivate students in learning.

It is not strange to find that a student who responded very well to questions during lessons fails to correctly respond to the same items when the word "test" or "examination" is attached to those items. Conversely, a student who remained dull in class during normal lessons may come out of test/examination with very high score. It is also observed that some students no matter the condition they find themselves, would be achieving fairly higher than others.

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Ethothi (2002) stated that students from active homes (homes that are ready to provide their wards with all they need to learn effectively) have high achievement motivation and consequently achieve higher academically while those from the same active homes who also have high achievement motivation may turn out to achieve low academically. Others too, from very poor background or dull homes may excel in almost all subjects despite the absence of some basic school requirements.

Under normal circumstance, a student would always want to be associated with high academic achievement as this brings some sort of prestige to him/her. But this is not happening in our colleges of education today where it is believed that all the students are adults and know why they are in school. However, some of the students are satisfied with even a weak pass/score. This indeed is an ugly situation (Ninty, 2003, Museen, 2014).

A pre-study investigation carried out by the researchers in Cross River State College of Education, Akamkpa provided startling revelations. The pre-study investigation was to find out the performance of four batches of Nigeria Certification in Education (NCE) graduands with respects to their performances in NCE programmes between 2018 and 2022. The result of the pre-study investigation shows that the total number of students admitted and the performance level keeps declining progressively year after year. The findings showed a gradual decline in average performance from 83.4% in 2018 to 41.95% in 2022.

The ugly situation resulting from poor performance of students has far reaching adverse implications for parents, lecturers, general public and the nation at large. Repeated poor performance according to Isangedighi (2007) and Joshua (2020) tend to generate a sustained and an ill-motivating environment which lowers the students need to achieve and within which they see themselves as helpless, resigned and unable to break a tradition of poor performance.

This may be so because their school needs a seldomly sufficiently provided, coupled with their poor health perhaps, improper diet, hunger and fear of failure; when these happen, students may begin to develop poor estimate of self, and see the world as hostile and unpredictable.

Ukpong (2020) and Ndili (2024) sees the school as a refined model of the society that is supposed to correct the lapses of the home and culture of the people. The school determines through the classroom activities, lecturers and course-mates the kind of motives and anxieties that will operate in the individual to help or deter the individual in his/her learning task.

A stimulating environment increases the students' curiosity to learn. Also, the teachers' professional use of motivational techniques could help the students' enthusiasm towards learning.

The development of anxiety among students differ according to the students involved and circumstance that the students find themselves. This is the view of Feshback (1971) who observed that when students are isolated from each other or loved ones, anxiety develops. The researcher further stated that the circumstances in which an individual student is threatened by a specifically personal element, such as an invasion of privacy or embarrassment due to social comparison or ridicule directs an individual attention towards himself. Thus, a tendency towards isolation is aroused and the need for affiliation decreases under this circumstance; the individual becomes anxious.

It should also be noted that too much information or provision of too many materials to be learnt can induce anxiety. Equally, insufficient or incorrect information can lead to what is called information anxiety.

Anxiety can be subdivided into basic, pervasive, mild, chronic and crisis anxieties. Each of the anxiety types affect the student in different ways. The effect can be negative or positive depending on the type.

Isangedighi (2007) explained that basic anxiety seem to be natural and affects almost everybody. It occurs when one has a horrific feeling and thus appear to be helpless or defend less as in infants or young children. As a reaction to such anxiety, the individual may need to move towards people (need for affection) or move away from people (need for independence) and need to move against people (need for power). However, if properly controlled, it could be useful in acquisition of more knowledge and thus led to higher academic achievement.

Mild anxiety is not too intense and can facilitate the acquisition of knowledge by students, because it arouses their interest in what they intend to do. Absence of this type of anxiety will result in lack of interest in academic achievement.

Chronic anxiety stems from an environment that is inconsistent, unjust, or harsh in which there is limitations to grow in self-reliance. Crisis anxiety is characterized by a state of high anxiety and turmoil, caused by fears, depression and feeling of uncertainty. It is common among students during examination/test.

Since anxiety is a state of mind and is also a form of behaviour affecting learners' achievement motivation/academic ability, there is need to investigate the cause, impact and how to cope or control such negative anxieties in learners. It is based on these that the researchers became inspired to carry out this research project.

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STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The current poor performance of students of Colleges of Education in Cross River State and in the nation at large has continued to pose very serious concerns to the governments, parents teachers and other stakeholders, especially when considered against the resources spent each year in these institutions. Thus, poor performance has also made it difficult for government to achieve their aim of making NCE the minimum teacher qualification as stated in the philosophy of Nigerian Education (NPE, 2008).

In response to the situation, some studies have been carried out by several researchers notably; Ethothi (2002), Joshua (2020), Ushie (2020), but tended to attribute the poor academic achievement of students generally to factors external to the students, such as teachers' commitment, insufficient provision of facilities etc. Obviously, very little consideration has been given to factors internal to the students, such as students' anxiety and achievement motivation levels towards academic work.

It is the researchers' belief that a careful and thorough research work has not been carried out in Cross River State on the effect of the type and level of anxiety and achievement motivation on the academic performance of College students. This is so because a quick look at the existing literature revealed that most information on anxiety and achievement motivation are foreign. Only very few studies especially those coming empirical basis have been conducted using Nigerian setting.

It is on the basis of these lack of indigenus literature on the two variables and the absence of careful and thorough research work on the variables of study that the researchers decided to embark on this research project.

Aims and Objectives of the Study.

The overall aim of this research work is to determine the impact of anxiety and achievement motivation on College of Education students' academic performance in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the following objectives were formulated to guide the study.

- Determine the impact on the type and level of anxiety on the academic performance of NCE students in Cross River State.
- Determine the impact on the type and level of achievement motivation on NCE students in Cross River State.

Research Hypotheses.

The following research hypotheses were tested in this study.

1. There is no significant influence of College students' state anxiety level on their academic performance.
2. There is no significant influence of college students' trait anxiety level on their academic performance.
3. There is no significant influence of college students' achievement motivation level on their academic performance.

Justification/Significance of the Study

Extensive research work has been conducted on anxiety and achievement motivation generally especially by foreign authors/researchers, notably, Burn Sten (1957), Atkinson and Litwin (1960), Dunn (1968), Byrne (1979), Kramer (1979) and Ethothi (2002). This implies that only few empirical research studies have been carried out by non-foreign researchers concerning influence of level of anxiety and achievement motivation on academic achievement, what is perhaps new is therefore what is stated to be lacking above. Thus, this research work sought to determine the impact or influence of anxiety and achievement motivation on NCE college students in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Based on this, the research is important for the following reasons:

- It is hoped that the result of this study and its recommendations will help course lecturers to know how and when to use the presence of anxiety and achievement motivation in the students to achieve more.
- The counsellors will know when students are negatively affected by both or either level of anxiety and/or achievement motivation and thus help them adjust.
- The parents/guardians will realize that the performance of their wards in Colleges of Education lies greatly on the foundation and encouragement that they give to them at home for development and maintenance of the right type of anxiety and achievement motivation.
- Most importantly, it will help the college students to know the type and level of anxiety and achievement motivation required for effective academic achievement in their various courses.

Scope of the Study

This research work is limited to Cross River State, Nigeria. However, any generalization of the results can be done in context of any geographical area having similar characteristics. Most importantly, the research work is limited in scope to the variables of study namely; two types of anxieties – trait and state anxiety and achievement motivation.

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Review of Related Literature

The literature shall be reviewed along the following themes:

- i. Trait anxiety and academic performance.
- ii. State anxiety and academic performance.
- iii. Achievement motivation and academic performance.

Trait anxiety and Academic Performance

When anxiety becomes part of a person's personality such anxiety could be regarded as trait anxiety. He is a perennially anxious person. Cattell and Khime (1977) sees trait anxiety as a permanent characteristic of some people, having common variables such as susceptibility to annoyance, lack of confidence in new skills, high emotional comments or highly temperamental.

Spielberger (1992) also conceives trait anxiety as a relatively enduring individual difference among individuals especially in learners, having almost all the attributes of state anxiety except that the attributes of trait anxiety are permanent in nature and affects students' academic and social achievement more. The level of anxiety an individual develops can either affect him positively or negatively as far as academic performance is concerned.

Mackeachie and Doyle (2002) observe that perennial anxiety (trait anxiety) in individuals interferes seriously with learning. This interference has to do with the level of development or first, mild anxiety which can facilitates learning to a point beyond which anxiety will no longer have any positive influence, indicating perennial anxiety has set in.

Bernard (1972) sees the probability that the negative handicapping emotion more often present in the classroom is perennial and sometimes chronic anxiety. Also, Oshorn (2003) disclose that excessive and perennial anxieties lead to inability of the student concerned to cope with situations as they would not allow him to make full use of his potentials.

This is in agreement with Tobia (2009) who reports that high and permanent anxiety students divide their attention between demands of the school task and pre-occupations with somatic concerns and self-references. Contributing also to the influence of trait anxiety and academic performance, Speilberger (1992) using Trailors (1973) Manifest Anxiety Scale (MAS) reports that high anxiety that is perennial impaired the grade point average (GPA) of university under-graduates of average academic aptitude.

From Turner's (1977) investigation, high levels of anxiety correlates with low intelligence quotient (IQ), lower school achievement and low self-esteem. However, the researcher noted that the correlation does not have a causal implication. The relationship between anxiety and intelligence quotient is according to him difficult to disentangle.

Ethothi (2002) stated that highly anxious students are particularly sensitive to their social environments and benefit more from the opportunity for observational learning. The researcher also pointed out that when materials to be learnt are organized, highly anxious students would perform relatively better than non-anxious students, especially when the learners are also spaced.

States Anxiety and Academic Performance

When anxiety is situation induced (i.e. type of task, time allowed for a task being too short, test or examination, noise etc.) it is said to be state anxiety.

In certain situations, a test anxious student may know the course material very well, but because of his level of anxiety, is unable to demonstrate his knowledge of the course during examination i.e. anxiety is seen to impair performance when it is situation-induced.

A review of the effects of anxiety on learning from instructions in a variety of setting by Ethothi (2002), ranging from traditional classroom based environment to individualized instructional contexts such as programmed computer-managed or assisted instruction revealed that anxiety interferes with students' performance from a variety of instructional methods.

Ogban (2001) reported that although sophisticated and computerized assisted instructions are lacking in most Nigerian tertiary institutions but where available, such materials can facilitate learning, expose the learners to the basics of the subject matter, understanding and self-confidence in their courses and performance will be improved.

However, Onwuegbu's (2009) findings reveal that under the more increased self-threatening conditions, the low anxious students performed much better than the high anxious students. This is consistent with Ethothi (2002) fin dings that children who are more anxious performed far less in a given task to decide their placement in streams of class.

Reed (1990) earlier noted that competent school work is more favoured by middle anxiety than extremely low or high anxiety students.

Also, Joe (2006) points out that the high test anxious students will normally ruminates over his or her inadequacy and become distracted by self-deprecatory thoughts and thus perform poorly. The researcher further states that the interfering effect on their anxiety could depress their performance level in test or examination. He however notes that at the other end of the scale, (in a relaxed and tense free atmosphere) high anxious students would perform better than low anxiety students.

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Research conducted by Ethothi (1990) reveals that students who develop coping ability for anxiety who are high test anxious students perform better in a test compared to those with non-coping and neutral coping students who are low test anxious. The implication is that students who are high test anxious and developed coping abilities were conscious of the fact that absence of anxiety and uncontrolled anxiety level would lead to poor performance, this probably led to the development of the coping abilities and hence, high performance.

Academic Achievement Motivation and Academic Performance

There is considerable evidence that achievement motivation indicates some relationship with academic performance.

Ezewu (2007) compared the performance of high and low scoring subjects on need for achievement on a scrambled-words test and arithmetic test. The subjects worked two minutes on a page and were to make a word out of each set of disarranged letters. On the scrambled words test, the high achievement group started at about the same performance level as the low achievement group but quickly improved their performance so that in the last of the 10 two minutes period they were unscrambling about half-again as many words as they had in the first 2 minutes interval.

The low achievement group however showed relatively little change over the 10 internals. Evidently, the high achievers learned to perform this task more quickly and efficiently over the time they worked on it, whereas the low achievers did not. This findings conform Ukpong (2020) postulation that: where learning is possible, subjects with strong achievement motivation learn faster as the task progresses and the skills thus acquired are facilitated by the achievement motive.

In the arithmetic test, Ezewu (2007) points out that neither of the two groups showed a performance gain over the period taken by the arithmetic test, although the high need achievers worked approximately 20 percent more problems in each time interval than the low need achievers.

Also, in the study conducted by Ogban (2001 elementary school pupils of equal ability but with different levels of need for achievement were subjected to an arithmetic task for a period of ten minutes. It was found from the scores obtained from the task that subjects high on the achievement motivation scale (as was determined through the TAT scale) performed significantly better on each practice period than subjects who were low on the achievement motive scale.

Joe (2006) in a study of the influence of achievement motivation on the academic achievement of first year undergraduate trainees in the University of Port Harcourt, found a correlation of 0.32 between achievement motivation score and the first year (GPA) scores of the students. Also Denga (2009) carried out a research study to find out whether specially designed curriculum to improve motivation for learning in school could increase performance. In his study, students were assigned to one experimental group and two controlled groups for forty sessions. The pre-test showed that the students did not differ significantly from one another in the need for achievement, but the test result revealed a significant difference in the mean score of three groups. The result also showed that special programmes such as special curriculum, counselling, involvement of learners in decision making in the school could improve learners' need for achievement.

Ibanga (2016) notes however, that the results of such programme training may not necessarily be fully attributed to the training, but could be for instance from a change in one's expectation of success instead of an increase in any basis of need for success.

However, although most studies have tended to find a strong relationship between achievement motivation and academic performance; there are other studies that have failed to find such typical relationship between increased achievement motivation and performance in school. The research observation by McClelland and Alachuler (1981), Brown (1990) and Joshua (2020) noted that it is not enough to conclude that performance in a variety of situations is enhanced by level of achievement motivation especially, when one considers that the two variables can be affected by several intervening variables.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Causal-comparative design which is purely a survey research type was adopted. This design also falls under ex-post facto which is non-experimental research type. In this type of research design the research does not have direct control of the independent variables as their manifestations occurred before the study is carried out and/or they cannot be easily manipulated (Kerlinger, 1986; Ibanga, 2016).

The design was also adopted because it is economical to study a representative of a group that would allow for acceptable generalization of results on the entire target population which would have been otherwise too expensive to study (Isangedighi, 2012).

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Research Area

The study area is Cross River State, Nigeria. Cross River State is one of the 36 states of Nigeria, and has its capital located within the southern senatorial zone, Calabar. Cross River has a total land mass of 21,156 kilometers square (km²) and a population of over four million people, with five (5) major ethnic groups namely; Efik, Yakurr, Ejagham, Bekwarra and Bette.

The state is made up of 18 local government councils and lies between latitude 5°32¹¹ and 4°27¹¹ North of Equator and longitude 7°5¹¹ and 9°28¹¹ East of Greenwich meridian.

The state is bounded to the North by Benue State, to the South by Bight of Bonny and the Atlantic Ocean, on the East by the Republic of Cameroon and to the West by Akwa Ibom, Abia and Ebonyi states. The state is endowed with a lot of tourist sites such as; the National Parks in Boki and Akamkpa, Obudu Ranch Resort, Afi mountains, Nkarasi monoliths in Ikom, the Kwa Falls in Oban area, the Nigerian Export Processing Zone (EPZ), Tinapa project, Standard Airport for both International and Domestic flights. Other distinctive features found in Cross River State include; the Federal and state Universities, Colleges of Education, many private/public primary and secondary schools.

Cross Riverians are engaged in diverse occupations for livelihood most of which are subsistence and commercial farming, business, fishing, civil/public service jobs among others. Also, Cross Riverians are pluralistic in spoken/written languages ranging from Efik, Ejagham and Bekwarra.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised of all students (male and female) in the two Colleges of Education used for the study. The two colleges are Federal College of Education, Obudu and Cross River State College of Education, Awi, Akamkpa.

Statistics show that the two colleges have an estimated population of 10,500 students as of the time of this research. However, students running degree programme, sandwich or the pre-NCE programme are excluded from the population.

Table I. Population: School by School

College	Location	Male	Female	Total
1. Federal College of Education	Obudu	2,100	3,800	5,900
2. Cross River State College of Education	Awi, Akamkpa	1,900	2,700	4,600
Total		4,000	6,500	10,500

Field Source: 2024.

Sample and Sampling Technique:

The sampling technique adopted was stratified random sampling technique that is multi-stage. Stratified sampling method or procedure was employed because of the heterogeneity of the population. Also, this method was used for fair representation of all elements/subjects in the sub-groups (NCE I, II and NCE III), and to increase statistical precision or reduce sampling error.

Simple random sampling method was used after stratification to select subjects in each batch of NCE in the two colleges. This method allowed members of the population equal chance of being selected without bias.

Thus, three (3) hundred students from each batch of NCE (NCE I, II and III) in the two (2) colleges were randomly selected giving a sample size of one thousand, eight hundred students.

Table II: School Sample Characteristics.

College	Male	Female	Total
1. Federal College of Education, Obudu	391	509	900
2. Cross River State College of Education, Akamkpa	380	520	900
Total	771	1,029	1,800

Field Source:

Instrument for Data Collection:

Two (2) research instruments were used for data collection namely;

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1. A structural questionnaire constructed by the researchers titled Anxiety Modified Intellectual Achievement Motivation Questionnaire (AMIAMQ). The questionnaire had four (4) sections with a total of 30 items, that boarders on subjects' demographic data, trait and state anxiety and achievement imagery.
2. Scores of subjects in the first semester examination of the 2023/2024 academic session.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments.

The instruments were subjected to preview and independent expert judgement for face and content validity. This was also based on the fact that all the lecturers involved in teaching and conducting semester examination are by NCCE minimum standard qualified.

Also, to ascertain applicability and reliability of the study instruments, a trail/field testing was conducted with 100 students randomly sampled from the population that was not used for the final study. A post-test was conducted after four (4) weeks interval, and the test-re-test reliability of each dimension of the study variables was computed. The results obtained showed an overall correlation of 0.82 for all dimensions of the sub-variables. This result therefore attest to the reliability of the instrument (Hagerty, 1971 and Joshua, 2005).

Table III: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient Test-re-test Reliability of each Dimension of the study variables.

Variables	N	No. of items	Testing X	SD	r	
Trait anxiety	100	10	1 st	24.54	6.32	0.97
			2 nd	24.11	5.5	
Trait anxiety	100	10	1 st	24.58	6.7	0.87
			2 nd	24.22	5.6	
Achievement motivation (Academics)	100	10	1 st	44.00	4.6	0.63
			2 nd	43.00	3.4	

Table V: Mean Scores and Differences in mean between the 1st and 2nd Tests of each of the study variables.

Variables	N	1 st Test Ex	2 nd Test Ex	1 st Test X	2 nd Test X	Diff. between 1 st and 2 nd
Trait anxiety	100	1914	1881	24.54	24.11	0.43
State anxiety	100	1917	1889	24.58	24.22	0.36
Academic Achievement Motivation	100	3401	3345	44.00	43.00	1.00

No pair of score has a mean difference of up to 2. The highest difference of 1.00 was observed in academic achievement motivation. This is quite insignificant considering the total number of subjects, items and weighting of items involved. There is therefore a positive correlation between the first and second tests in all the dimensions of the study variables, and thus adequate enough to be used.

Statistical Analysis of Data

The data obtained from the field for this study was analysed using descriptive statistics analysis of variance (ANOVA). All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Description of Research Variables.

The study was conducted on the impact of anxiety and achievement motivation on Colleges of Education students' academic performance in Cross River State. The major independent variable of the study is students' anxiety level while the dependent variable is college students' academic performance. The descriptive statistics variables in the study are shown in Table IV.

Table IV: Means and Standard Deviations of major variables in the study.

S/No.	Variable	N	Means (x)	SD
1.	Anxiety	1,800	22.23	3.06
2.	Achievement motivation	1,800	22.03	2.82
3.	Students' academic performance	1,800	24.68	2.09
	Total	1,800	11,543	9.16

Presentation/Interpretation of Results.

Hypothesis one (1): This was stated as there is no significant influence of college students' state anxiety level on their academic performance. The independent variable in this hypothesis is college students' state anxiety level (which has three levels of high moderate and low), while the dependent variable is college students' academic performance (which is sum of the students' T-Transformed scores on the 1st semester externally moderated examination). The statistical analysis technique used in testing this hypothesis was one-way analysis of variance. The result is shown in Table 5.

Table V: Analysis of Variance of the influence of College Students' state anxiety level on their academic performance.

Groups (levels)	N	Mean	SD
Low	400	49.85	9.88
Moderate	900	56.49	9.59
High	600	58.06	9.83
Total	1,800	58.37	9.73

Source of variation	sources of square	Df	Means square	F-ratio
Between Groups	76.19	2	38.09	
Within Groups	70834.812	1798	94.82	0.40**
Total	70911.002	1797		

Not significant at 0.05 level (critical F with df of 2 and 1797 = 3.00).

The analysis of result in Table V shows that the calculated f-ratio of 0.40 is less than the critical f-ratio of 3.00, indicating that the null hypothesis is not reject. This implies that the variation in the observed mean values of 49.85 (for low level), 56.49 (for moderate level) and 58.06 (for high level) are merely due to chance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of college students' trait anxiety level on their academic performance.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is college students' trait anxiety (which has three levels of high, moderate and low), while the dependent variable is college students' academic performance. The statistical analysis technique used in testing this hypothesis was one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The result of testing is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Analysis of variance of the influence of college students' trait anxiety level on their academic performance.

Groups (levels)	N	Mean	SD
1. Low	500	49.67	9.45
2. Moderate	900	50.46	9.58
3. High	400	51.09	10.57
Total	1,800	50.37	9.73

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Source of variation	Sum of Squares	df	mean squares	F-ratio
Between groups	165.83	2	82.92	
Within groups	70706.23	1797	94.65	0.88**
Total	70872.06	1798		

Not significant at 0.05 level (critical F with df 2 and 1797 = 3.00)

The analysis of result in Table 6 shows that the calculated F-ratio of 0.88 is less than the critical F-ratio of 3.00. This implies that the null hypothesis is not rejected indicating no significant influence of trait anxiety level on the academic performance of college students. This also implies that the observed variations in mean values of 49.67 (for low level) 50.46 (for moderate level) and 51.09 (for high level) are merely due to chance.

Hypothesis 3: This was stated as, there is no significant influence of college students' level of academic achievement motivation on their academic performance.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is college students' academic achievement motivation level (which three levels of high, moderate and low). The dependent variable is college students' academic performance. The statistical analysis technique used in testing this hypothesis was one-way analysis of variance. The result is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Analysis of variance of the influence of college students' academic achievement motivation level on their academic performance.

Groups (level)	N	Mean	SD
Low	470	54.98	9.01
Moderate	510	54.05	9.96
High	820	53.04	10.08
Total	1,800	54.73	9.73

Source of variation	Source of squares	Df	Mean squares	F-ratio
Between Groups	84.82	2	41.91	
Within Groups	71828.18	1798	95.77	0.43**
Total	72910.06	1797		

***Not significant at 0.05 level (critical F with df of 2 and 1797 = 3.00)*

The analysis of result in Table 7 shows that the calculated F-ratio of 0.43 is less than the critical F-ratio of 3.00 rejecting the null hypothesis. This implies that, there is no significant influence of academic achievement motivation level on the academic performance of college students.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

State Anxiety level and Academic Performance

The result revealed no significant influence of college students' state anxiety level on their academic performance. The findings of non-significant difference agrees with the view of the researchers that different levels of state anxiety do not significantly influence academic performance of learners.

The finding is similar to the results obtained by Eriksen (1964), Ethothi (1990), Ethothi (2002) and Museen (2014) who found that when test or examination is stress free, examiners are warm, permissive and understanding, the high anxious groups would perform academically better, though the mean value might not be significant.

The findings also agrees with research results of Nenty (2003) who observed that the highly anxious students performed better than the less anxious when evaluation stress is low, even on naturally occurring tests.

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However the result contradicts the research finding of Wine (1991) and Tobia (2009) all of who noted that high anxiety interferes negatively with academic performance. Perhaps, this could result from learners being intimate with their lecturers than it was before, also during test or examination stress free situation, level of maturity of the learners, and adequate pacing of the examination timetable.

According to arousal theory (Bourne, Exastrand and Dominowski (1971) the highly state anxious students are expected to perform as well as those who are confident and are not disturbed by the lecturers' interference of any sort. This implies that performance of learners in many tasks is related to the level of those learners arousal.

Other possible factors accounting for non-significance in the group difference could be seating arrangement of the learners during examination (or test), and lecturers emphasizing some areas of revision before examinations, as well as the fact that examinations are internally prepared.

Trait Anxiety and College Students' Academic Performance

The result in hypothesis II also stipulated that there is no significant influence of college students' trait anxiety level on their academic performance. The finding of no significance agrees with some previous research results. For example Meyer (2000) noted that anxiety does not significantly influence the academic performance of students with different intelligent quotient. He observed that intelligence played a more significant role than anxiety.

This findings also supports the earlier research work of Meckeackie and Doyle (1982) and Ezewu (2007) who saw anxiety as double edge sword which sometimes leads to high academic performance and sometimes deter academic performance. Trait anxiety can deter progress in academic work according to Osborn (2003) when anxiety becomes excessive and perennial, a situation where the learner no longer make use of his/her full academic potentials.

Some plausible reasons could be suggested for this findings: these include chance factor, sitting arrangement during examinations, nature of the courses offered and "sorting" by most of the students. The finding also agrees with Sarason (2002) who discovered that learners who develop coping ability for anxiety who are highly anxious perform better in a test compared to those with non-coping and natural coping learners who are also low test anxious.

Students' Academic Achievement Motivation level and Academic Performance

The results of statistical testing of hypothesis III shows that the difference in the mean scores of college students with low, moderate and high levels of academic achievement motivation is not significant. The finding contradicts many other research findings in this area, notably those of McClelland (1955, 1965), Lovell (1952), Ezewu (2007), Joe (2006), Ibanga (2016) and Ukpong (2020), etc. all postulated that where learning is possible, subjects with strong academic achievement motivation learn faster as the task progress than the low or moderate anxiety learners.

However, the findings confirms the earlier research study by Rosen (2001) who observed that when intelligence is controlled through analysis of covariance, no significant relationship would be observed between academic achievement motivation and the subjects' academic performance. The research findings also agrees with Armstrong (2005) who observed that the highly anxious learners most times become prone to indecision and error or tend to ignore relevant information thereby achieving very low.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study investigated the extent to which anxiety and achievement motivation influences the academic performance of college education students in Cross River State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted, which made use of a simple size of 1,800 NCE students from two (2) Colleges of Education in the study area using a multi stage/stratified random sampling procedure.

Also, two research instruments were employed to test three (3) research hypotheses that were formulated to guide the study. One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyse the data obtained from the field.

On the basis of the findings, it was concluded as follows:

1. Different levels of state anxiety among learners (college students) do not significantly influence their academic performance. However, learners with moderately high state anxiety level show some level of superiority in academic performance over the moderate and low state anxiety level.
2. The level of trait anxiety among learners (college students) does not significantly influence learners' academic performance. Though research also indicates that learners with moderately high anxiety performed better compared to others (with moderate and low trait anxiety).
3. College student's academic achievement motivation level does not significantly influence their academic performance. However, certain level of achievement motivation is required for effective learning (Ukpong, 2020 and Joe (2016)

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The researchers however recommended strongly that, counselling services and programme in the college should be very sensitive to psychological interest and values of the learners since they are enduring traits on which their academic performance should be based.

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